

Kinetics and Mechanism of Substitution of Aquo-ligands from *cis*-Diaquo-bis-oxalatochromate(III) Ion by Glycine in Ethanol—Water Mixture of varying Dielectric Constants

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Kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands from *cis*-diaquo-bis-oxalatochromate(III) ion by glycine have been studied in the pH range 4–7.4, where glycine remains in zwitterionic form. The reaction is first order with respect to the [complex] and also [glycine]. The second order rate constants (k_2) and the corresponding activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) in 20, 30 and 40% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures were evaluated and SN_2 path has been suggested

SUBSTITUTION of aquo-ligands from *cis*-diaquo-bis-oxalatochromate(III) ion has been attempted earlier.

Banerjea and Roy¹ studied the reaction of *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ with bipyridine and *o*-phenanthroline, and suggested concurrent reagent-independent and reagent-dependent paths of associative nature. Kelm and Harris² suggested associative interchange mechanism for the substitution by oxalate. However, anation of the same *cis*-[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ ion by picolinate³, dipicolinate⁴ and quinolinate⁵ takes place via an 'A' path. The present study relates to the substitution of aquo-ligands from *cis*-diaquo-bis-oxalatochromate(III) ion by glycine.

Experimental

cis-K[Cr(Ox)₂(H₂O)₂].2H₂O (Complex-I) was prepared following known method⁶ and its purity was checked. The complex showed maximum absorbance at 416 and 562 nm in full agreement with the literature values⁷; the corresponding ϵ values were found to be 67.2 (lit. 68.5) and 50.0 (lit. 51.0) respectively. Chromium and oxalate found were 14.84 (calcd. 15.34) and 50.9% (calcd. 51.9%). Solutions of glycine and the complex of desired concentration were prepared in three different ethanol-water mixtures (20, 30 and 40%, v/v). The pH values of the reaction mixtures were adjusted with perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide.

The product of the reaction between Complex-I and glycine at pH 5.0, was prepared by mixing the aqueous solutions of the two reactants and refluxing on a water-bath for several hours. It was finally evaporated on a water-bath and the resulting solid was recrystallised from 40% ethanol (Found: Cr, 15.0; N, 4.02. Calcd. for: Cr, 15.19; N, 4.09%); λ_{max} at 415 ($\epsilon=74.8$) and 555 nm ($\epsilon=61.4$). The product complex (Complex-II) revealed its composition as 1 : 1 (M : L). Composition of the Complex-II in solution was further checked by Job's method of continuous variation.

In all experiments A.R. grade chemicals and double-distilled water were used. An Elico LIHOT pH-meter was used to measure pH. A Beckman D.B.G spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Kinetic run: The course of the reaction was followed by measuring absorbance at 530 nm where substantial difference exists in absorption of Complex-I and the product. The pseudo-first order rate constants for substitution reaction were obtained by plotting $\log [(D_\infty - D_0)/(D_\infty - D_t)]$ against time, D_∞ , D_0 and D_t being optical density values after completion of reaction, at the beginning and at the end of time t respectively. The rate constant values were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variation of Complex-I concentration on rate constant: The concentration of Complex-I was varied from 0.01 to 0.02 M at a constant excess concentration 0.2M of glycine in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture. Ionic strength (0.5M), pH (5.0) and temperature (60°) were also kept constant. It was observed that the rate of reaction is first order with respect to [Complex-I],

$$-\frac{d[\text{Complex-I}]}{dt} = k_{obs} [\text{Complex-I}]$$

Effect of variation of pH on rate constant: The concentration of the Complex-I, glycine and ionic strength (μ) were kept constant at 0.01, 0.1 and 0.5M respectively, and pH was varied from 4.0 to 7.4 at a fixed temperature 60°; the solvent used was 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture. The pH-dependence of rate constant (Table I) indicates that the rate constant value increases slowly with increase of pH upto 6.0, and beyond pH 6.0, it increases rapidly with the increase of pH.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF pH ON REACTION RATE

pH	4.0	4.5	5.0	6.0	6.5	7.4
$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$	5.52	5.95	6.34	8.06	23.33	46.52

For glycine, $pK_1=2.34$ and $pK_2=9.6$ at 25° . Hence the effect of pH on rate above pH 6.0 is due to the following acid dissociation equilibrium,

where, pK'_1 value⁹ is 7.1 at 25° . The hydroxoquo complex is much labile due to π -bonding ability of OH^- which facilitates the replacement of water molecules in the reaction, hence the rapid increase in rate above pH 6.0.

Effect of ionic strength on rate constant : The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was adjusted with sodium perchlorate considering the net charge on glycine to be zero (isoelectric nature). The concentrations of Complex-I and glycine were kept constant at 0.01 and 0.1 M respectively at pH 5.0 and at 60° in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture and ionic strength was varied. The rate of reaction increased with increase of μ . The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to be 3.13, 4.84, 5.66, 6.10, 6.34, $6.86 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at ionic strengths 0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.8 M respectively.

The slight increase in rate with increase in μ may be interpreted as a case of non-specific ionic strength effect. Similar effect was observed by Hamm and Davis¹⁰ in the study of anation reactions of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ by different organic acid anions. This type of non-specific medium effect was also observed by Brown and Harris¹¹ and Niogy and De¹².

Effect of varying glycine concentration on rate constant : At a fixed $[\text{Complex-I}]$ of 0.01 M, $\mu=0.5$ M and pH=5.0, the $[\text{GlyH}]$ was varied in the range 0.1–0.3 M at 45, 50, 55 and 60° in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture. The same experiment was repeated at 50, 55 and 60° in two solvent medium (20 and 40% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture). In each case k_{obs} (Table 2) increased linearly with increase in $[\text{GlyH}]$ at a particular temperature and solvent medium (Fig. 1). In order to explain such a variation in rate with change in $[\text{GlyH}]$, the following reaction scheme can be proposed :

when (at a given pH),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_2 [\text{GlyH}] \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Dependence of k_{obs} on glycine concentration at different temperatures: (A) 45° , (B) 50° , (C) 55° and (D) 60° ; solvent 30% (v/v) EtOH/ H_2O mixture, $[\text{Complex-I}] = 0.01$ M, pH=5.0.

where, k_2 is the second order rate constant. The values of k_2 (Table 3) at different temperatures and solvent media were evaluated from the slope of the straight lines found by plotting k_{obs} vs $[\text{GlyH}]$.

Effect of dielectric constant on rate constant : The reaction was studied in three different ethanol-water mixtures and at four different temperatures. The k_2 values increased with the increase in concentration of the organic component at a particular temperature as shown in Table 3.

Association between the charged substrate complex and the zwitterionic ligand glycine through the negative end of its dipole, was favoured in a medium of low dielectric constant (D). For each particular temperature a plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/D$ is linear with a positive slope (Fig. 2). As the temperature was increased, the magnitude of slope decreased. All these facts can be explained by the simplified Laidler-Eyring equation¹³ for the effect of dielectric constant on reaction rates,

$$\frac{d \ln k_2}{d(1/D)} = \frac{z^2 e^2}{2kT} \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r^*} \right)$$

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT WITH [GlyH] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN DIFFERENT ETHANOL-WATER (% v/v) MEDIUM

[Complex-I]=0.01 M, $\mu=0.5$ M, pH=5.0

[GlyH] M	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$									
	45°		50°		55°			60°		
	30%	20%	30%	40%	20%	30%	40%	20%	30%	40%
0.10	1.68	1.83	2.78	4.41	3.04	3.95	5.30	4.98	6.34	7.90
0.15	2.42	2.75	4.23	6.62	4.56	6.03	7.95	7.48	9.49	11.91
0.20	3.51	3.80	5.74	8.83	6.08	7.89	10.60	9.97	12.67	15.89
0.25	4.18	4.59	7.06	11.03	7.60	9.87	13.25	12.47	15.84	19.85
0.30	5.10	5.51	8.33	13.25	9.13	11.72	15.40	17.96	18.96	23.20

TABLE 3—VALUES OF k_2 IN DIFFERENT ETHANOL-WATER MEDIUM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ethanol % (v/v)	$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1})$			
	45°	50°	55°	60°
20	—	1.83	3.04	4.99
30	1.68	2.82	3.95	6.34
40	—	4.42	5.30	7.94

Fig 2. Plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/D$ at temperatures (A) 50°, (B) 55° and (C) 60°.

where, D is the dielectric constant of the medium, ze the ionic charge of one of the reactants while ionic charge of the other reactant is zero, r the effective radius of the charged reactant and r^* the radius of the activated species, and k the Boltzman constant.

The positive slope of the lines obtained by plotting $\log k_2$ vs $1/D$, indicates that $r^* > r$, i.e. the rate-determining step is associative in nature.

Effect of temperature on anation rate constant
Table 4 shows that the ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values decrease as the dielectric constant of the medium decreases. For the association process, ΔH^\ddagger should decrease as the concentration of organic component in the medium increases. An increase in the organic component affects the solvation of activated species and ground state of reacting species. An isokinetic plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger is linear and it may be inferred that the similar transition states are found in the studied range of composition of solvent pair.

Mechanism and conclusion: Anation reaction of $cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^-$ with glycine in zwitterionic form involves association between the complex anion and the negative end of the ligand zwitterion. In the rate-determining step both bond-making and bond-breaking are important. Anation rate is much faster (Table 4) than isotopic water exchange rate¹⁴ of Complex-I, so bond-making is important. Rapid increase in anation rate above pH 6.0 can be explained as $cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)(OH)]^{2-}$ is formed above pH 6.0, and the ligand OH^- being a strong π -donor facilitates the loss of coordinated water ligand. Thus bond-breaking also has an influence on rate-determining step.

The above conclusion is very much supported by the results obtained in the variation of dielectric constant. The positive slope of the linear plot of

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT SOLVENT MEDIA WITH WATER EXCHANGE PROCESS

System	Medium (v/v% of ethanol-water)	Rate constant at 25° $s^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔH $\text{kJ}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
$cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^-$	20	1.13×10^{-4}	86.69 ± 2.5	-29.89 ± 7.5
	30	2.10×10^{-4}	78.50 ± 2.5	-52.33 ± 7.5
	40	3.39×10^{-4}	73.92 ± 2.5	-63.60 ± 7.5
$cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^- + H_2O$ (isotopic water-exchange)		$7.78 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$	75.36	-90.00

$\log k_2$ vs $1/D$ (Fig. 2) indicates that the radius of the activated species is greater than the radius of the charged reactant (Complex-I) according to the Laidler-Eyring equation. Moreover, the small decrease in ΔH^\ddagger with the increase in dielectric constant of the medium can be explained as a medium with higher dielectric constant diminishes the possibility of association between the Complex-I and negative end of the reactive glycine molecule and automatically needs some higher energy of activation.

Thus in the present system, ligand substitution occurs by a process of association (S_N2) where both bond-breaking and bond-making have importance.

References

1. D. BANERJEA and J. ROY, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1973, **399**, 115.
2. H. KELM and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 706.
3. S. MAZUMDAR and K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 277.
4. S. MAZUMDAR and K. DE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1986, **55**, 437.
5. S. MITRA (MAZUMDAR) and K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 592.
6. W. G. PALMER, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1954, p. 387.
7. K. V. KRISHNAMURTY and G. M. HARRIS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 213.
8. S. W. FOX and J. F. FOSTER, "Introduction to Protein Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1957, p. 26.
9. C. SCHENK, H. STIEGER and H. KELM, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1972, **391**, 1.
10. R. E. HAMM, R. L. JOHNSON, R. H. PERKINS and R. E. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4469.
11. P. M. BROWN and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1872.
12. B. K. NIOGY and G. S. DE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1983, **92**, 153.
13. K. J. LAIDLER and H. EYRING, *Ann. NY Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **39**, 303.
14. H. STIEGER, G. M. HARRIS and H. KELM, *Ber. Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 262.